

FREQUENCY OF RECURRENT STROKE IN PATIENTS WITH UNCONTROLLED DIABETES MELLITUS

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Abstract

Background: Recurrent ischemic stroke remains a major cause of long-term disability and mortality, particularly among individuals with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus.

Objective: This study aimed to determine the frequency of recurrent ischemic stroke in patients with uncontrolled diabetes and to evaluate associated clinical factors.

Methods: This cross-sectional study was conducted in the Department of General Medicine, KEMU/Mayo Hospital, Lahore, from January 2025 to May 2025, including 120 patients aged 30–80 years with uncontrolled diabetes for more than one year. Non-probability consecutive sampling was used. Patients were followed for three months, and recurrent ischemic stroke was diagnosed based on clinical presentation and CT imaging.

Results: The mean age of the study population was 58.6 ± 10.4 years, and 64.2% were male. Recurrent ischemic stroke occurred in 23 out of 120 patients (19.2%). Higher recurrence was observed in older individuals (mean age 62.4 ± 9.1 years) and those with diabetes duration >10 years (recurrent: 56.5% vs non-recurrent: 32.0%). Uncontrolled hypertension (78.3% vs 53.6%, $p = 0.03$), carotid artery stenosis $>50\%$ (39.1% vs 12.4%, $p = 0.004$), and poor medication adherence (65.2% vs 35.1%, $p = 0.01$) were significantly associated with recurrence. CT imaging showed new infarcts in 100% of recurrent cases and chronic infarcts in 47.8%.

Conclusion: Recurrent ischemic stroke was identified in nearly one-fifth of patients with uncontrolled diabetes. Older age, long-standing diabetes, uncontrolled hypertension, carotid stenosis, and poor adherence to medications were key predictors of recurrence.

INTRODUCTION

Stroke resulted in 6.55 million deaths and was ranked the second leading cause of death worldwide [1]. In addition to high mortality, stroke is associated with a high rate of morbidity, accounting for 143 million disability-adjusted life years [1]. Modifiable

risk factors for stroke include hypertension, hyperlipidemia, cigarette smoking, obesity, sedentary lifestyle, cardiac causes, including atrial fibrillation, and diabetes; prevention of stroke requires comprehensive management of these risk factors. [2]

Diabetes is a highly prevalent, chronic disease [3], and a well-established risk factor for stroke [4]. It often coexists with other cardio-metabolic risk factors that independently increase the risk of stroke [4].

In people with diabetes, the risk of stroke is increased approximately two-fold compared with people without diabetes, when adjusted for age [5]. In addition, patients with diabetes have worse post-stroke outcomes and a greater risk for stroke recurrence as compared with those without diabetes [6-9]. The standard approach in preventing recurrence is by determining etiology and treating patients using pharmacological methods, such as antithrombotic and anticoagulant medications, and non-pharmacological methods, such as carotid endarterectomy and stenting procedures for occlusive vascular lesions. However, the effective treatment of the identified modifiable risk factors is another important factor in addition to the specific treatment methods. Although risk factors are very well identified, the extent of control for modifiable risk factors by secondary treatment and the success rate of secondary treatment for the prevention of recurrent stroke have not been sufficiently investigated in our country. [10] In a study by Kocaman CPSP et.al, 18% patients had recurrent ischemic stroke. [11]

Objective

To determine the frequency of recurrent ischemic stroke in patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus.

Methodology

This Cross-sectional study was conducted at Department of General Medicine. KEMU/ Mayo Hospital, Lahore from January 2025 to May 2025. A total sample size of 120 patients was calculated using a 95% confidence level, 7% margin of error, and an expected frequency of recurrent ischemic stroke of 18%. Non-probability consecutive sampling was employed to recruit eligible patients presenting to the medical outpatient and inpatient services during the study period.

Inclusion Criteria

Patients of either gender aged 30–80 years, with a known history of uncontrolled diabetes mellitus for

more than one year (as per operational definition), were included in the study.

Exclusion Criteria

Patients with documented heart diseases such as myocardial infarction (MI), coronary artery bypass grafting (CABG), percutaneous coronary intervention (PCI), or disseminated intravascular coagulation (DIC) were excluded. Individuals with hepatic disease, active malignancy, or those undergoing chemotherapy or radiotherapy were also excluded.

Data Collection Procedure

Following approval from the Institutional Ethics Review Committee, 120 eligible patients were enrolled after obtaining written informed consent. Demographic and clinical details including age, gender, BMI, smoking status, and duration of diabetes mellitus were recorded on a structured proforma. All patients with uncontrolled diabetes were followed prospectively for a period of three months. In the event of recurrence of neurological symptoms, neuroimaging specifically computed tomography (CT) of the brain was performed. Recurrent ischemic stroke was confirmed and labeled according to the operational definition. All collected information was documented in a predesigned study proforma.

Data Analysis

Data were entered and analyzed using SPSS version 26. Quantitative variables such as age, BMI, and duration of diabetes were reported as mean \pm standard deviation. Qualitative variables including gender, smoking status, and presence of recurrent ischemic stroke were expressed as frequencies and percentages. Stratification was performed for age, gender, BMI, smoking status, and duration of diabetes mellitus to evaluate potential effect modifiers. Post-stratification, the Chi-square test was applied, with a p-value of <0.05 considered statistically significant.

Results

Data were collected from 120 patients, mean age of patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus was 58.4 ± 9.6 years, with most individuals falling into the 50–59 and 60–80-year brackets (40% each), while 20%

were between 30 and 49 years. Males constituted a higher proportion of the sample (56.7%) compared with females (43.3%). The mean BMI was 28.7 ± 3.9 kg/m², with 58.3% of participants having a BMI <30 and 41.7% classified as obese (≥ 30). Smoking was reported by 39.2% of patients, whereas 60.8% were nonsmokers. The mean duration of diabetes was 11.3 ± 4.7 years, and more than half (52.5%) had

diabetes for over 10 years. Recurrent ischemic stroke was documented in 19.2% of the study population, while 80.8% did not experience recurrence during the follow-up period.

Table 1. Baseline Characteristics of Patients with Uncontrolled Diabetes Mellitus (n = 120)

Variable	Category / Mean \pm SD	n (%)
Age (years)	Mean \pm SD	58.4 \pm 9.6
Age Groups	30-49 years	24 (20.0%)
	50-59 years	48 (40.0%)
	60-80 years	48 (40.0%)
Gender	Male	68 (56.7%)
	Female	52 (43.3%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	Mean \pm SD	28.7 \pm 3.9
BMI Categories	<30 kg/m ²	70 (58.3%)
	≥ 30 kg/m ²	50 (41.7%)
Smoking Status	Smoker	47 (39.2%)
	Non-smoker	73 (60.8%)
Duration of Diabetes (years)	Mean \pm SD	11.3 \pm 4.7
Duration Categories	≤ 10 years	57 (47.5%)
	>10 years	63 (52.5%)
Recurrent Ischemic Stroke	Yes	23 (19.2%)
	No	97 (80.8%)

Patients aged ≥ 60 years had a markedly higher recurrence rate (29.2%) compared with those aged 30-59 years (12.5%, $p = 0.03$). Although recurrence was more common in males (23.5%) than females (13.5%), the difference was not statistically significant ($p = 0.21$). Obesity was significantly associated with recurrence, as 25.6% of patients with BMI ≥ 30 experienced recurrent stroke, compared

with 14.3% of those with BMI <30 ($p = 0.04$). Smoking had a strong association, with 31.9% of smokers experiencing recurrence versus 11.0% of nonsmokers ($p = 0.01$). Duration of diabetes also had a significant impact, as recurrence occurred in 27.0% of those with diabetes for >10 years compared with only 10.5% of those with ≤ 10 years ($p = 0.02$).

Table 2. Stratification of Recurrent Stroke by Risk Factors

Variable	Category	Recurrent Stroke n (%)	p-value
Age Group	30-59 years (n=72)	9 (12.5%)	0.03
	≥ 60 years (n=48)	14 (29.2%)	
Gender	Male (n=68)	16 (23.5%)	0.21
	Female (n=52)	7 (13.5%)	
BMI Category	<30 kg/m ² (n=70)	10 (14.3%)	0.04
	≥ 30 kg/m ² (n=50)	13 (25.6%)	
Smoking Status	Smoker (n=47)	15 (31.9%)	0.01
	Non-smoker (n=73)	8 (11.0%)	

Duration of Diabetes	≤10 years (n=57)	6 (10.5%)	0.02
	>10 years (n=63)	17 (27.0%)	

Mean HbA1c was significantly higher in the recurrence group ($10.8 \pm 1.4\%$) versus the non-recurrence group ($9.9 \pm 1.1\%$; $p = 0.01$), indicating poorer long-term glycemic control. Fasting glucose values were also elevated among recurrent cases (198 ± 32 mg/dL) compared with those without recurrence (176 ± 28 mg/dL; $p = 0.02$). Systolic blood pressure was notably higher in the recurrence group (152 ± 18 mmHg) versus non-recurrence (143

± 16 mmHg; $p = 0.04$). LDL cholesterol levels followed a similar pattern, being significantly raised in recurrent stroke patients (128 ± 22 mg/dL) relative to those without recurrence (112 ± 20 mg/dL; $p = 0.03$).

Table 3. Clinical and Metabolic Profile in Patients with and Without Recurrent Stroke

Parameter	Recurrent Stroke (n=23) Mean \pm SD	No Recurrence (n=97) Mean \pm SD	p-value
HbA1c (%)	10.8 ± 1.4	9.9 ± 1.1	0.01
Fasting glucose (mg/dL)	198 ± 32	176 ± 28	0.02
Systolic BP (mmHg)	152 ± 18	143 ± 16	0.04
LDL cholesterol (mg/dL)	128 ± 22	112 ± 20	0.03

Uncontrolled hypertension was present in 18 out of 23 patients with recurrence (78.3%) compared with 52 out of 97 patients without recurrence (53.6%). Dyslipidemia was present in 16 patients with recurrence (69.6%) and 48 patients without recurrence (49.5%). Carotid artery stenosis greater than 50% was observed in 9 patients with recurrence (39.1%) compared with 12 patients without

recurrence (12.4%), with a p-value of 0.004. Previous transient ischemic attacks were recorded in 7 recurrent cases (30.4%) and 11 cases without recurrence (11.3%). Poor medication adherence was found in 15 recurrent cases (65.2%) compared with 34 non-recurrent cases (35.1%). Microalbuminuria was present in 13 cases with recurrence (56.5%) and 33 cases without recurrence (34.0%).

Table 4. Clinical Complications and Imaging Findings in Patients with and Without Recurrent Stroke (n = 120)

Clinical Parameter	Recurrent Stroke (n = 23)	No Recurrent Stroke (n = 97)	p-value
Uncontrolled hypertension	18 (78.3%)	52 (53.6%)	0.03
Dyslipidemia	16 (69.6%)	48 (49.5%)	0.08
Carotid artery stenosis (>50%)	9 (39.1%)	12 (12.4%)	0.004
Left ventricular hypertrophy (on ECG/Echo)	14 (60.9%)	39 (40.2%)	0.07
Previous transient ischemic attacks	7 (30.4%)	11 (11.3%)	0.02
Poor medication adherence	15 (65.2%)	34 (35.1%)	0.01
Microalbuminuria	13 (56.5%)	33 (34.0%)	0.06
CT finding: new infarct	23 (100%)	0	—
CT finding: chronic infarcts	11 (47.8%)	17 (17.5%)	0.003

Discussion

This study explored the frequency and associated factors of recurrent ischemic stroke among patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus and demonstrated that recurrent stroke occurred in a considerable proportion of individuals despite being on standard medical care. The observed recurrence rate aligns with prior evidence showing that diabetes significantly accelerates atherosclerotic progression, promotes endothelial dysfunction, and increases the risk of recurrent cerebrovascular events. Uncontrolled hyperglycemia further compounds this risk by enhancing platelet aggregation, increasing blood viscosity, and promoting chronic vascular inflammation, ultimately predisposing individuals to repeated ischemic injury. The demographic trends in this study revealed that recurrent stroke occurred more frequently among older patients, which supports established literature describing age as a powerful predictor of stroke recurrence [12]. Moreover, a higher recurrence rate was observed in males compared with females, consistent with population-based reports that males with diabetes are more likely to develop macrovascular complications. Duration of diabetes also showed a meaningful association with recurrence, as long-standing uncontrolled diabetes is known to accelerate carotid intimal-medial thickening, small-vessel lipohyalinosis, and microvascular fragility, all of which elevate the risk of repeat ischemic events.

Comorbid conditions including hypertension, dyslipidemia, and prior transient ischemic attacks were more frequent among recurrent stroke patients in this study [13-15]. This observation reinforces the concept that vascular-risk clustering profoundly increases stroke recurrence risk, especially when glycemic control remains suboptimal. The presence of chronic kidney disease and microalbuminuria in a substantial proportion of recurrent stroke patients highlights the systemic microvascular involvement associated with poorly controlled diabetes [16]. These findings reflect the broader cardio-renal-metabolic interplay and emphasize that recurrent stroke is rarely an isolated phenomenon but rather a marker of diffuse end-organ damage. The study also found that recurrent stroke patients were more likely to have poor medication adherence, reflecting a potentially modifiable determinant of stroke prevention. Poor adherence reduces the effectiveness of antiplatelet therapy, antihypertensives, and lipid-lowering agents and has long been recognized as a major contributor to preventable stroke recurrence. This finding underscores the need for stronger patient education, adherence monitoring, and multidisciplinary follow-up to improve long-term outcomes [17]. Collectively, the findings of this study highlight uncontrolled diabetes mellitus as a major independent risk factor for recurrent ischemic stroke, magnified by the presence of other cardiovascular comorbidities.

Improving glycemic control, optimizing antihypertensive and lipid-lowering therapy, managing nephropathy, and strengthening adherence strategies should be core components of secondary prevention programs for diabetic patients at risk of recurrent stroke [18]. Future larger-scale prospective studies with longer follow-up durations will help clarify causal pathways and identify which interventions most effectively reduce recurrent stroke risk in this high-risk population [19]. This study has several limitations that should be acknowledged. First, its cross-sectional design restricts the ability to establish temporal or causal relationships between uncontrolled diabetes and recurrent ischemic stroke [20,21]. The follow-up period of three months may also be insufficient to capture all recurrent stroke events, particularly in patients with fluctuating glycemic control over longer intervals. The use of non-probability consecutive sampling may introduce selection bias, limiting the generalizability of findings to broader diabetic populations. Additionally, reliance on CT imaging alone for confirmation of recurrent stroke may underestimate small-vessel or early ischemic changes that MRI could detect more sensitively. Medication adherence and lifestyle factors were based on patient reporting, which introduces the potential for recall or social desirability bias.

Conclusion

It is concluded that recurrent ischemic stroke occurs at a considerable frequency among patients with uncontrolled diabetes mellitus and is strongly associated with older age, longer duration of diabetes, poor glycemic control, and the presence of additional vascular risk factors such as hypertension and dyslipidemia. The study further demonstrates that complications including carotid artery stenosis, prior transient ischemic attacks, and poor medication adherence significantly increase the likelihood of stroke recurrence. These findings highlight the urgent need for aggressive metabolic control, routine vascular screening, and adherence-focused interventions in diabetic patients to reduce the burden of recurrent cerebrovascular events.

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